

PREVENTION OF IMPORTANT NON-COMMUNICABLE DISEASES AMONG THE POPULATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7559625>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 11th January 2023

Accepted: 22th January 2023

Online: 23th January 2023

KEY WORDS

Chronic diseases, cancers, preventions, healthy lifestyle.

ABSTRACT

Non-communicable diseases (NCDs) - diseases of a non-infectious nature, for example, cancer, cardiovascular diseases, type 1 and 2 diabetes mellitus and chronic respiratory diseases, as well as their risk factors, are a growing problem in the field of development and public health in Uzbekistan. This article offers factual data confirming that NCDs contribute to a reduction in the volume of production of the population; it also discusses possible options for preventive measures aimed at solving this problem.

Modern medicine refers to the most common non-infectious pathologies:

1. Chronic heart and vascular diseases.
2. Respiratory tract diseases (COPD, asthma, etc.).
3. Type 1 and type 2 diabetes mellitus.
4. Malignant and benign cancer.

According to statistics, NCDs (non-communicable diseases) are detected most of all in countries with an average standard of living of the population, therefore, prevention of non-communicable diseases today is one of the priorities of joint activities, society and various medical and social communities. Every year, 40 million people die from NCDs in the world - this is 70% of all deaths. Every year in the world, more than 17 million people under the age of 70 die from non-communicable pathologies, 87% of which fall on states with an average and low standard of living of residents. Among all causes of mortality from NCDs, heart and vascular diseases are leading, followed by oncological pathologies, respiratory tract diseases and diabetes mellitus. Smoking, physical inactivity, unbalanced diet, alcohol consumption - these adverse factors are directly related to the likelihood of developing non-communicable diseases. Medical examination, examinations, diagnosis and treatment of NCDs, palliative care for patients are the main components of the prevention of chronic non-communicable diseases. Prevention of non-communicable diseases is one of the most important ways to combat non-communicable pathologies is targeted activities to reduce all risk factors. Today, there are solutions that allow the government and other stakeholders to reduce the impact of risk factors that are susceptible to external influence. Monitoring trends and progress in the fight against non-communicable diseases plays a special role in developing such measures and

setting priorities. The prevention of chronic non-communicable diseases, the demographic change towards the aging of the population, the changing environmental situation creates new problems related to the preservation and strengthening of public health, reducing the role of NCDs and increasing their importance for harming people and society. The procedure for organizing and implementing the prevention of non-communicable diseases and carrying out measures to promote a healthy lifestyle in medical organizations. This significantly strengthens the regulatory framework of measures aimed at reducing mortality from cardiovascular, bronchopulmonary, oncological diseases and diabetes mellitus. The procedure systematizes measures for the formation of a healthy lifestyle, the diagnosis of diseases and risk factors for their development during preventive examinations and annual medical examinations, as well as dispensary observation of patients. It also discusses the main issues of prevention of NCDs and the formation of a healthy lifestyle in children and adolescents. It is planned to pay increased attention to the elimination of such negative factors as poor nutrition, physical inactivity and smoking. There are several levels of prevention of non-communicable diseases:

- individual;
- group;
- population.

There are 2 ways to prevent NCDs:

1. Development and implementation of programs to promote healthy lifestyle and prevention of major non-communicable diseases, including by reducing the negative impact of risk factors for their development;
2. Carrying out measures for the prevention and early diagnosis of NCDs, risk factors for their occurrence (including earlier identification of risk factors for alcohol abuse and the use of narcotic and psychotropic drugs not according to the doctor's indications), measures to correct the identified risk factors, as well as the organization of dispensary observation of citizens with NCDs or high-risk Measures for the prevention of non-communicable diseases.

Prevention of non-communicable diseases includes the following measures:

- sanitary and hygienic education;
- conducting information and communication activities dedicated to the management of healthy lifestyle, prevention of NCDs and the use of psychoactive substances;
- identification of violations of the basics of healthy lifestyle, prerequisites that contribute to the development of non-infectious pathologies (smoking, alcohol, drugs and psychotropic drugs), determining how dangerous they are to the health of a particular patient;
- elimination of risk factors for NCDs, prevention of their complications (referral of patients to consultations of narrow specialists or to specialized institutions);
- medical examination and annual occupational examinations;
- organization of dispensary observation of patients with diagnosed non-communicable diseases (including those with heart and vascular pathologies).

Based on the results of the first stage of medical examination, the therapist determines which of the three health groups the patient belongs to, plans the tactics of his medical supervision, if necessary, sends him to the second stage of medical examination. Therapist, pediatrician or family doctor: identifies and eliminates the main risks of developing NCDs

through counseling, diagnosis, referral to preventive offices and departments, as well as to specialists of a narrow profile according to the identified disease, condition or risk factor; participates in medical examinations and occupational examinations; organizes and conducts dispensary monitoring of patients with NCDs, directs patients with high risks of cardiovascular pathologies to preventive offices and departments, health centers, etc.; keeps records of patients undergoing occupational examinations with other specialists. At this level, the prevention of non-communicable diseases is carried out by specialized doctors-specialists in the direction of other health workers or with self-treatment, as well as in the process of dispensary observation of patients with NCDs. Children, adults and the elderly should deal with risk factors that contribute to the development of non-communicable diseases, such as unhealthy diet, insufficient physical activity, exposure to tobacco smoke or harmful alcohol consumption. The development of these diseases is influenced by factors such as aging, rapid unplanned urbanization and the globalization of unhealthy lifestyles. For example, the globalization of such a phenomenon as unhealthy diet can manifest itself in individuals in the form of high blood pressure, elevated blood glucose, elevated blood lipids, overweight and obesity. These conditions are called intermediate risk factors that can lead to the development of cardiovascular disease. To reduce the impact of NCDs on people and society, a comprehensive approach is needed, requiring the joint work of all sectors, including health, finance, international relations, education, agriculture, planning and others, in order to reduce the risks associated with NCDs, as well as to carry out prevention and control measures.

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